

Appendix 3: Results from citizen science survey ([Survey 1](#), [Survey 2](#), [Survey 3](#)) of *Areca triandra* records in Sri Lanka conducted through the Facebook pages of ‘Flower of Sri Lanka’ and ‘Medicinal plant identification’ with 130 participants.

District	Town/village	Habitat type	
Gampaha	Pugoda	Distributed in the area, Suburban areas, Home gardens	
	Meethirigala, Pilikuththuwa	Forest site	
	Kotugoda, Ganepola, Attanagalla, Radawana, Minuwangoda, Katana, Ja-Ela	Home gardens	
	Divulapitiya, Negombo, Ragama	Distributed in the area	
	Mirigama	Distributed in the area, Home gardens	
	Kirindiwela, Wattala	Suburban areas	
	Basnagoda	Near the reservoir	
	Nittambuwa, Negombo, Raddolugama		
	Colombo	Waga, Welikanna, Indikada Mukalana, Labugama Kalatuwawa	Forest site
		Hokandara	Distributed in the area, Home gardens, Estate lands
Piliyandala, (e.g. Maviththara)		Suburban areas, Home gardens	
Pelawatta		Suburban areas	
Around Avissawella <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Salawa Estate: Alupotha Division, Salawa Division, Kanampella Division ● Halpe Estate, Halpe Division, Hewagama Division, Waga Division ● Ayr Estate, Ayr Division, Gurudola Division, Labugama Division ● Divurumpitiya Estate, Lower Division, Upper Division 		Distributed in Avissawella area, small forest patches in rubber estates	

	Seethawaka	Forest sites
	Homagama	Suburban areas
	Kotikawatta, Malabe, Thalahena , Athurugiriya, Wellampitiya	Home gardens
	Kaduwela	Fences in the garden
	Nugegoda, Thummodara	
Kalutara	Horana, Panadura, Bandaragama	Home gardens
	Matugama,	Distributed in the area, Abandoned lands
	Yagirala, Dombagaskanda	Forest site
	Walallawita,	
Galle	Kanneliya, Nakiyadeniya	Forest site
	Balapitiya,	Near Madu gaga
	Elpitiya	Distributed in the area, Home gardens
	Udugama, Tellambura, Hapugala	Distributed in the area
	Galagoda Atta, Poddala, Kalegana, Wakwella , Rumassala, Tawalama	Home gardens
	Hapugala, Hiniduma,	
Matara	Akurugoda	Fences in the garden
	Akuressa	Distributed in the area, Estate lands
	Dandeniya	Forest site near expressway
Kandy	Nawalapitiya	Home gardens

	Udawattekele Sanctuary, lower Hanthana, Dunumadalawa,	Forest site
	Sirimalwaththa;	
Kegalle	Kannaththota,	Home gardens
	Ruwanwella,	Distributed in the area, Home gardens
	Deraniyagala, Kitulgala;	
Nuwara- Eliya	Ginigathhena;	Home gardens
Ratnapura	Kalawana	Distributed in the area, Home gardens
	Kiriella	Home gardens
	Dumbara Manana	Forest site
	Waddagala	Roadside near the forest
	Kuruwita, Nivithigala	
Kurunegala	Uhumeeya	Near roadside
	Boyagane	Homegarden